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THE GREAT PASCHAL CYCLE WITH COMMENTARIES AND ORDER BY TBEL ABUSERIDZE

The Great Paschal Cycle with Commentaries and Order by Tbel Abuserisdze (1190–1240) places him at the forefront of Georgian astronomical and mathematical sciences. The main objects of his scientific interest in the work are the Great Paschal Cycle and the ecclesiastical calendar as the basis of orthological and liturgical practices.

The Great Paschal Cycle with Commentaries and Order is devoted to the great indication (532-year cycle), calendar features, and chronological questions. The text answers the question why the fasts of Greeks and Georgians coincide, while the Greek calendar is 96 years behind Georgian (Greeks count 5508 BC, and Georgians – 5604).

According to Tbel Abuseridze's scientific research, the Georgian and Greek paschal-computational systems were originally designed with specific numerical data from the creation of the world in mind and in line with computational data.

Based on strict mathematical principles, this event ensured the same result and the simultaneous holding of moving church holidays (R. Chagunava).

Tbel Abuserisdze offers interesting observations in terms of comparing Paschal data with astronomical analogues. In Paschalia, for example, the length of the moon is 29.5 days. Tbel Abuserisdze doubts this indicator and notes that in nature ‘the moon will not fully grow for twenty-nine days and a half.’

Indeed, no one among astronomers today disputes that, due to the eccentricity of the lunar orbit, the length of the synod month fluctuates by several hours (currently the synod month is 29.5305889 days). Therefore, M. Brosset et K. Kekelidze rightly noted that in 1233, when Tbel Abuserisdze wrote his work, Georgians already knew half of the errors that forced Pope Gregory XIII in 1582 to correct the calendar.

The Great Paschal Cycle with Commentaries and Order is at the same time a textbook, which has a special place among the monuments of ancient Georgian pedagogical literature. In the

form of visuals, the paper has two tables attached – a complete 532-year Paschal table (the Great Paschal Cycle) and a compact Paschal table (or Syryan Cycle).

Technical signs and footnotes are provided in the text and tables, which also explain and substantiate various issues related to the calendar and Pascal calculations. Instead of the dry declarations of formulas that were characteristic of medieval teaching literature, Tbel Abuserisdze offers students a methodologically progressive resource for conscious perception, showing the cause-and-effect connection between the facts.

The paper shows that after the Armenian-Georgian ecclesiastical schism (first half of the 7th century), the changes made to the Georgian ecclesiastical-liturgical calendar (introduction of the 5604-year-old nation and Paschals orientation on the Annunciation–weekday) were deeply understood by Georgian scholars from the very beginning, including both calendar-mathematical and theological (dogmatic-polemical) aspects.

Ioane Shavteli's iambic poetry, especially his use of the term Annunciation– weekday clearly shows that the scientific problem posed in the Great Paschal Cycle was still under discussion in Vardzia school, where Tbel Abuserisdze was educated.

References

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